

Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy

Author: Giorgi Barakadze

Research paper: Argumentative essay

Educational programme: "Medicine"

First year

Tbilisi

2024

Plagiarism

In the modern world plagiarism is one of the most challenging issues of our time in the sphere of education and scientific activity. In this essay I will try to cover why Individualism and creativity have a critical value to the society. Plagiarism is when one presents works, ideas scientific approaches from other sources as one's own with or without the original author's permission consent, authorization without giving proper credit and full acknowledgement. Plagiarism harms the society as it weakens individuality, creativity, and ethics. To understand why all these aspects are essential for us, it is important to become aware of their values in the society.

Firstly, being an individual means to accept and express truly own traits, values, and views. It also implies one's uniqueness, involves the author's responsibility for his/her actions and effects on others, but also it means freedom to follow one's own original path and to make independent decisions. It is important to say that individuality significantly contributes to one's personal development and self-discovery to embrace self-identity and to learn how to be authentic. Moreover, development an appreciation for one's singularity might help to forge stronger, more meaningful bonds with other people.

For instance, Eleanor Roosevelt once said: "Remember always that you have not only the right to be an individual, but you also have an obligation to be one. You cannot make any useful contribution in life unless you do this." Her words support the idea of individuality and underlines our obligation to be our selves no matter what consequences are followed.

In fact, individuality ignites creativity, by generating distinct viewpoints and ideas that mold the multifaceted terrain of our world. The process of coming up with new ideas or concepts, or making new connections between already-existing ideas, and then putting those ideas and conceptions into practice to produce something innovative and unique is creativeness, imaginativeness, and innovativeness.

In this modern technologically well-developed world, everybody has social media which is full of content creators. There are three main types of them: those who create original content and share it by their own creative minds; those who take popular posts or audio materials and modify them partially using their creative minds; and those who simply copy content without adding any originality or thought of their own. The representatives of the last group are those who just copy the ideas and creative works of others and pass them off as their own. They don't strive to be innovative or use their own creative abilities. This type of behavior makes social media monotonous and uninteresting.

On the other hand, in the world where every creative and colorful endeavor is appreciated and respected, innovation flows freely and has no boundaries. Artists, philosophers, and dreamers come together to paint boundless imagination; each color added to it, creates a new composition, gives a new meaning, and adds depth to the painting they develop. In the modern society creativity and individualism are the best ways to foster connections and the development of ourselves and our world by making it more colorful.

Building up on this, Intellectual property, which is typically defined as non-physical property resulting from creative thoughts, can be impacted by utilizing someone else private works, such as research papers or abstracts, without their consent or without appropriate credit. This is significant because it takes so much effort to create and taking that work without giving credit is unethical. It is theft both morally and legally. Every human being has unique intellect that may create a fresh and distinct vision; all it takes is hard work, unceasing effort, to get the desired outcome. It is completely unethical to violate both intellectual property rights through plagiarism. Individuals' labor needs to be safeguarded, and the degree of fabrication must be kept to a minimum.

On the basis of the above, it can be concluded that plagiarism is an outright violation of intellectual property. It attempts to pass off someone else work as their own, undermining the creative process and the fundamentals of independence and inovativeness. We must value uniqueness and recognize the time and effort that people put into their creations, just as famous artists throughout history have devoted their lives to refining their skill and creating their own distinctive styles that generated history, culture, and made the world more colorful.